

ON THE MATRIX CRACKING MODE IN ADJACENT PLYS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Damage mode of matrix cracking in plies adjacent to the cracked ply in composite laminates is highlighted in this study. Static tension tests of $[0/\theta/90]_s$ and $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates with $\theta=30^\circ$, 45° , and 60° are conducted in order to investigate matrix cracking behaviors in multiple plies. Matrix cracks developed along the fiber direction are the dominant damages observed in $[0/30_2/90]_s$ laminate, whereas a high density form of matrix microcracking is mainly observed in θ° plies of the other laminates. The laminate configuration, e.g. ply angle and ply thickness, turns out to have significant effect on the damage mode in the adjacent plies. Simplified analysis for the mechanical behavior of laminates containing developed matrix cracks in multiple plies is presented. Finally, finite element analysis for the classification of the damage modes in adjacent plies is provided in order to evaluate the experimental observation.

KEYWORDS: Matrix cracks, Multiple ply damages, Crack interaction, X-ray radiography, Finite Element Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Considerable attention has been paid to intralaminar matrix cracking, which grows parallel to the fibers within a ply block in composite laminates, for two or three decades [1-3]. Accumulation of matrix cracks induces the deterioration of mechanical performance, other modes of damage (e.g. delamination, fiber breakage), and pathways of chemical substances. Therefore, good understanding of the damage process of transverse cracks is necessary for evaluating the performance and durability of composite laminates.

Recently, the application of CFRP laminates to the cryogenic propellant tanks is a key topic for discussion in relation to the development of light-weight future reusable/expendable launch vehicles [4]. Basic research on the feasibility of cryogenic composite propellant tanks indicates that matrix crack onset and its accumulation are inevitable due to mechanical loads during operation in addition to severe thermal residual stress, and through-thickness connection of the matrix cracks causes unallowable propellant leakage [5]. Because of this, matrix cracking behaviors in multiple plies have to be clarified in order to provide the adequate guideline for cryogenic composite tank design.

In this paper, matrix cracking behaviors in plies adjacent to a cracked ply are studied. The emphasis is placed on the experimental/analytical understanding of effects of the ply thickness and the intersecting angle of the cracked plies on the matrix cracking mode in the adjacent plies. $[0/\theta/90]_s$ and $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates with $\theta=30^\circ$, 45° , and 60° are utilized for uniaxial tensile tests in order to observe cracking behaviors in θ° plies beyond the onset of 90° ply cracking. The difference of the cracking mode in the adjacent plies among laminate configuration is experimentally observed and summarized in terms of laminate geometry. Simplified analysis for the mechanical behavior of laminates containing developed matrix cracks in multiple plies is presented. Finally, the damage mode in adjacent plies are discussed by calculating energy release rates associated with θ° ply crack growth in the presence of 90° ply cracks using finite element analysis.

EXPERIMENT

Specimens

In order to investigate the matrix cracking behaviors in plies adjacent to a cracked ply, $[0/\theta_n/90]_s$ ($n=1,2$) laminates with $\theta=30^\circ$, 45° , and 60° were prepared. The material used in this study was IM600/#133, an intermediate modulus carbon fiber and toughened epoxy system, supplied by Toho Tenax. All specimens were 250[mm] long with 50[mm] GFRP end-tabs, leaving a 150[mm] gauge section. Due to the shear-extension coupling of the whole laminate characteristics, specimen width was configured to be 15[mm] in order to assure that there are enough regions of uniform deformation. Therefore, the observed region of matrix cracks was set to be 40[mm] in the middle part of the specimens.

Experimental Procedures

Quasi-static tensile tests were performed using an Instron8802 hydraulic-driven loading machine at a crosshead speed of 0.5[mm/min] at room temperature. Strain gauges were attached to the specimens for measuring axial strains. When the specimens were loaded to the predetermined strain levels, zinc iodide penetrant was applied to the free-edges and the specimens were held at half level of the applied strains for five minutes. The specimens were removed from the machine followed by X-ray radiography in order to inspect the cracking patterns. These specimens were then loaded to the next strain levels. Repeating these steps, the matrix cracking patterns in $[0/\theta/90]_s$ and $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates were obtained as a function of applied laminate strains.

Experimental Results

The first observed damage mode was transverse cracking in 90° ply followed by crack induction in θ° ply in all specimens. Crack accumulation behaviors in $[0/30_2/90]_s$, $[0/45_2/90]_s$, and $[0/60_2/90]_s$ laminates are shown in Fig. 1. It should be pointed out that a high density form of matrix microcracking could be observed in θ° plies for $\theta=45^\circ$ and 60° when 90° ply cracks initiated and developed in the fiber direction. At higher strain levels, microcracks increased in number in conjunction with the 90° ply crack increase for $\theta=60^\circ$, and a few microcracks grew in the fiber direction for $\theta=45^\circ$. In contrast, microcracks were barely observed in $[0/30_2/90]_s$ laminates and developed 30° ply cracks appeared. In this study, microcracks are defined as cracks that are induced by a single 90° ply crack and show no growth to the next 90° ply cracks, whereas developed cracks are cracks that propagate across multiple 90° ply cracks. These results indicate that the intersecting angle of the cracked plies has significant effects on the process of crack formation in the adjacent plies. When the

intersecting angle (i.e. $90^\circ - \theta^\circ$) is small, microcracks are observed before propagating in the fiber direction as is the case for $\theta = 45^\circ$ and 60° . However, developed cracks mainly form in the case of a large intersecting angle. Some specimens were inspected by X-ray CT-scanning in order to check the through-thickness extent of microcracks in θ° plies [6]. Cross-sectional images near crack intersections indicated that microcracks extend across the ply thickness as soon as they form. Therefore, it can be concluded that microcracks in θ° plies develop across the ply thickness followed by their propagation in the fiber direction.

Results of X-ray inspection of $[0/\theta/90]_s$ laminates are presented in Fig. 2. A high density form of matrix microcracking, which did not appear in $[0/30_2/90]_s$ laminates, could be observed in $[0/30/90]_s$ laminates as shown in Fig. 2. In $[0/45/90]$ and $[0/60/90]_s$ laminates, numerous microcracks in 45° and 60° plies follow matrix cracking in 90° ply. Most of the microcracks in 45° ply never extended to the fiber direction in $[0/45/90]_s$ laminates, as opposed to the case of $[0/45_2/90]_s$ laminates, in which some microcracks grew in the fiber direction.

Fig. 1: Crack accumulation behaviors in $[0/30_2/90]$ (left), $[0/45_2/90]$ (center), and $[0/60_2/90]$ (right)

Fig. 2: Crack accumulation behaviors in $[0/30/90]$ (left), $[0/45/90]$ (center), and $[0/60/90]$ (right)

Table 1 summarizes the experimental results indicating the dominant damage mode observed in θ° plies. It can be concluded that microcracks in θ° plies are more susceptible to formation in $[0/\theta/90]_s$ laminates than in $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates. The smaller intersecting angle and the thinner thickness of θ° ply lead to the more susceptibility to microcrack formation in the adjacent plies. Both the intersecting angle of the cracked plies and the θ° ply thickness (or

thickness ratio of θ° ply to 90° ply) turned out to have significant effects on the dominant damage mode in plies adjacent to a cracked ply.

Table 1: Summary of experimental results on the dominant damage mode in θ° ply

Intersecting angle		[0/ θ /90]s	[0/ θ_2 /90]s
$\theta=30^\circ$	60°	micro/developed	developed
$\theta=45^\circ$	45°	micro	micro/developed
$\theta=60^\circ$	30°	micro	micro

ANALYSIS

Simplified Analysis of Laminates with Matrix Cracks in Multiple Plies

Laminates with developed matrix cracks in multiple plies as the case of [0/30₂/90]s laminate are considered in this section. Many analytical models have been developed for the stress/strain and stiffness analysis of laminates containing developed matrix cracks in a single ply block. Using these analytical models combined with ply-by-ply homogenization technique [7-9], overall thermo-mechanical properties of the cracked laminates and energy release rates associated with crack formation can be estimated analytically. In this section, another approach is presented utilizing stress analysis of laminates with obliquely-crossed matrix cracks [10] and lamination theory.

Consider a symmetric laminate consisting of $2n$ plies. Ply indices are numbered consecutively from the top (1) to the bottom ($2n$). Ply- k has thickness of t_k and matrix cracks with uniform densities of ρ_k completely traversing in the fiber direction. Matrix cracks in the ply- k and the ply- $(2n+1-k)$ are assumed to be symmetrically arranged with respect to the middle surface. In this study, ply- k ($k=2\sim n-1$ and $n+2\sim 2n-1$) is divided into halves. The ply-1 and the upper ply-2 are assembled as group-1, the lower ply-2 and the upper ply-3 are as group-2 and so forth. Therefore, the whole laminate can be divided into $2n-2$ groups. Because of the symmetry, the group- k and the group- $(2n-1-k)$ are assembled again as sublaminates- k . This procedure is described in Fig. 3(a) and (b) in the case of a laminate consisting of eight plies. The eight-ply laminate can be divided into six groups, which, in turn, are assembled as three sublaminate as shown in Fig. 3(b). Each sublaminates has configuration as a $[\phi_m/\phi_n]$ s laminate. Thus, the sublaminate are regarded as $[\phi_m/\phi_n]$ s -type laminates with matrix cracks in both layers. Exactly speaking, each sublaminates may not be mechanically equivalent to a $[\phi_m/\phi_n]$ s -type laminate, because stress transfer in the cracked sublaminates is affected by other sublaminate. Nevertheless, this study utilizes this daring approximation in order to handle the complex problem of laminates with matrix cracks in multiple plies analytically.

Overall in-plane thermomechanical properties of a $[\phi_m/\phi_n]$ s laminate with obliquely-crossed matrix cracks can be evaluated analytically using the previously developed analytical solutions [10]. When overall thermomechanical properties of each sublaminates are obtained, the cracked sublaminates- k can be replaced with the effective sublaminates- k with thickness of $t^{(k)}$ and in-plane stiffness of $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)}$ (and coefficients of thermal expansion of $\bar{\alpha}_i^{(k)}$) as shown in Fig. 3(c). Then, application of lamination theory to the effective sublaminate results in evaluation of overall properties of the whole cracked laminate as shown in Fig. 3(d). Overall in-plane thermomechanical properties of general laminates containing of matrix cracks in multiple plies can be analytically predicted. In order to check the validity of the present method, a GFRP [0/90/-45/45]s laminate containing matrix cracks in all plies is considered in reference to finite element analysis of Ref.[11]. Comparison of the predicted mechanical

properties between the present analysis and FEA is shown in Fig. 4. The predicted stiffnesses using the present scheme agree well with the results of finite element analysis.

Fig. 3: Analytical procedure for the evaluation of effective thermomechanical properties of general laminates with matrix cracks in multiple plies

Fig. 4: Comparison of the predicted mechanical properties of GFRP laminate with matrix cracks in all plies between the present model and FEA[11]

Finite Element Analysis for Classification of Damage Mode in Adjacent Plies

Consider a $[0/\theta_m/90_n]_s$ laminate containing obliquely-crossed cracks, i.e. θ° and 90° ply cracks. In order to discuss stress distributions and boundary settings, it is spontaneous to utilize the oblique coordinate system along θ° and 90° ply cracks. The detailed analytical procedure is given in Ref.[12]. It is assumed that: 1) 90° ply cracks propagate completely in the fiber direction and are regularly distributed with crack density of ρ_2 ; 2) θ° ply cracks are symmetrically arranged with respect to the central plane, all of which have length $2a \sec \theta$ (projected length $2a$) propagating equally in the fiber direction from the 90° ply crack tips and uniform crack density of ρ_1 ; 3) The θ° ply crack tips are straight along the thickness direction. Therefore, a representative volume of $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates with developed matrix cracks in 90° ply and microcracks in θ° plies is defined as shown in Fig. 4 and three-dimensional finite element analysis is performed in order to calculate energy release rates associated with crack growth in θ° ply. Crack densities ρ_{90} and ρ_θ , which are defined in Fig. 5, are set to be $2[1/\text{cm}]$ and $5[1/\text{cm}]$, respectively, and mechanical strains corresponding to 1.0% in the 0° direction are applied in addition to residual thermal strains for numerical examples. Eight-node isoparametric elements are used in this study and double nodes are arranged in the crack surfaces and θ -ply crack length is controlled by fixing the corresponding double nodes. The material properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 2 and ply thickness is set to be $0.14[\text{mm}]$.

Calculated energy release rates associated with θ° ply crack propagation are shown in Fig. 6 as a function of crack length in the cases of $[0/30_2/90]_s$ and $[0/60_2/90]_s$ laminates. For comparison, the values associated with θ° ply crack growth without 90° ply cracks are also presented. It can be seen that mode-I energy release rates increase at the vicinity of 90° ply cracks due to the existence of 90° ply cracks. Schematics of the calculated mode-I energy release rates associated with θ° ply crack growth in the presence of 90° ply cracks are shown in Fig. 7. The solid line indicates energy release rates in the presence of 90° ply cracks and the dashed line indicates those without 90° ply cracks. When 90° ply is cracked, energy release rates associated with θ° ply crack growth reveal the maximum value at the vicinity of 90° ply crack. In contrast, there is no peak without 90° ply crack. When crack length increases, energy release rates reach the plateau value, which is identical between the cases with and without 90° ply cracks. The large difference between the maximum and plateau energy release rates causes stable growth of microcracks (observed as microcracks), whereas small difference (or the case that has no peak) results in the formation of developed cracks because of unstable crack growth.

Fig. 5: Representative volume of a $[0/\theta_m/90_n]_s$ laminate with developed matrix cracks in 90° ply and microcracks in θ° plies

Fig. 6: Energy release rates associated with θ -ply crack propagation as a function of normalized projected crack length in $[0/\theta/90]_s$ laminates with $\theta=30$ and 60 compared with the case without 90 -ply cracks

In order to investigate the dominant damage mode in θ° plies, the energy release rate ratio (maximum energy release rate divided by plateau energy release rate) is calculated as a function of angle θ in the cases of $[0/\theta/90]_s$ and $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates. Note that, when there is no peak in the energy release rate diagram, energy release rate at crack length where energy release rate show the peak in other cases (almost equal to half thickness of θ° ply) is utilized as the numerator of the energy release rate ratio. Fig. 8 shows the comparison of the energy release rate ratio as a function of θ between $[0/\theta/90]_s$ and $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates. In both cases, the energy release rate ratio increases in conjunction with decrease of intersecting angle between θ° and 90° plies (i.e. increase of angle θ). In addition, the energy release rate ratios of $[0/\theta/90]_s$ laminates is higher than those of $[0/\theta_2/90]_s$ laminates. Therefore, the smaller intersecting angle and the thinner thickness of θ° ply result in the larger energy release rate ratio, and thus, the higher susceptibility to microcrack formation in θ° plies in the presence of 90° ply cracks. Experimental observation of cracking behaviors in θ° plies, which was summarized in Table 1, coincides well with the above-mentioned discussions.

Fig. 7: Schematics of the relationship between crack length and energy release rate

Fig. 8: Effects of intersecting angle and θ' ply thickness on the energy release rate ratio

CONCLUSIONS

Damage mode of matrix cracking in plies adjacent to the cracked ply in composite laminates was experimentally investigated using CFRP laminates with different layup configuration. Matrix cracks developed along the fiber direction were the dominant damages observed in $[0/30_2/90]_s$ laminate, whereas a high density form of matrix microcracking was mainly observed in the other laminates. It was observed that the smaller intersecting angle and the thinner thickness of the adjacent ply led to the more susceptibility to microcrack formation in the adjacent ply.

Simplified analytical methodology of laminates with developed matrix cracks in multiple plies and finite element analysis for classification of damage mode in the adjacent plies were presented. Calculation of energy release rates associated with crack growth in the adjacent ply indicated that the difference between the maximum and plateau energy release rates may classify the damage mode in the adjacent plies, which was correlated with the experimental observation.

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